

The Determinants Of The Privilege Of Direct Execution In Administrative Law (A Comparative Study Between Jordan, Egypt And France)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 01, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: January 24, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Direct Execution Privilege, Administrative Decision, Administrative Law</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4628341</p>	<p><i>To achieve the public interest and ensure the regular and steady functioning of public facilities, the legislature gave the administration the privilege of resorting to direct implementation. This privilege is considered an exception to the general rule that stipulates that the administration's resort to direct implementation is through the judiciary, and the administration's use of this privilege assumes that the administrative decision enjoys legitimacy in the beginning. Therefore, the administration's use of this privilege is subject to conditions and limitations that the administration must abide by.</i></p>

Introduction

The formulation of the theory of proof in the administrative law on the basis of the circumstances of this law and the nature of the administrative lawsuit - which the administrative judiciary is concerned with - relates to administrative ties in which the administration is a party. It is dominated by the principle of legality, which means that the administration submits in all its actions to the rule of law, and in a way that suits this distinctive nature of administrative cases, and is compatible with it in order to achieve administrative justice. This is because the administration cannot be considered a regular party in any dispute in which it is involved. This is due to the vital role played by the administration and the supremacy of the goal that it seeks to achieve, so it enjoys certain privileges, with which there is no equitable balance between the two parties.

These privileges did not come in vain. Rather, they were dictated by the nature of the work carried out by the administration. The administration as a legal person from the public law person's logic assumes that it is far from the host of what is being defendant. This is to achieve the public interest, while individuals seek to achieve personal benefit or ward off harm, and that these privileges enjoyed by the administration have a real impact on the progress of the administrative case, and on the role of the administrative judge in the case.

The decisions issued by the administration are considered an effective concession, so the administration enjoys the privilege of direct implementation, which transfers the decision from the administrative theoretical stage to the practical application stage. This is through implementation without the need for permission from the judiciary, and the impact that this has on the rights of individuals and conflicts with human rights principles, so it has been briefed about some restrictions that limit resorting to it at any time.

•The study Problem:

Represented in the determination of the extent of the administration's commitment to the controls and determinants in activating the privilege of direct execution in the event that the administration resorted to activate it, the fact that the administration resorted to it without going back to the judiciary to obtain a court ruling on that, and the impact of this on human rights.

• The importance of study:

It comes through a statement of theories that dealt with the legal nature of the privilege of direct execution in administrative law and its impact on human rights, and a statement of the judicial conditions that must be met in order to resort to the privilege of direct implementation by the administration.

• Objectives of the study:

Reaching a statement of the meaning of the direct execution franchise and its advantages for management, and the legal nature of it by explaining the theories that dealt with it, and showing the legal and judicial controls that the management must adhere to, and the management's right to revoke this privilege.

Study questions:

This study aims to answer the following questions:

1. A statement of the concept of the privilege of direct execution and its advantages for management?
2. Determine the theory most appropriate for the application of the privilege of direct execution?
3. A statement of the conditions for applying the franchise of direct execution?

Method of the study:

The comparative approach between Jordan, Egypt and France will be followed in preparing this research by extrapolating the rulings, legal texts, and the jurisprudential opinions of legal researchers.

We will address the determinants of the privilege of direct execution in administrative law as follows:

What is the direct execution privilege, the nature of the direct execution privilege, the controls for applying the direct execution privilege?

What is the direct execution franchise?

What is meant in general is the implementation of administrative decisions and the transfer of the administrative decision from the theoretical administrative stage to the realm of practical application, and the administration is distinguished with regard to the decisions issued by it with multiple advantages, and we address this through two requirements as follows:

The concept of direct execution franchise

Direct implementation means that the administration has the right to determine its rights by individuals according to administrative decisions it issues and implements by its own will, without the need for judicial intervention.(1)

It is the right of the administration to execute its orders against individuals by force without the need for prior permission from the judiciary (2). That is, the administration, with the privileges of the public authority, has the right to directly implement its decisions in the event that individuals refrain from doing so voluntarily, or there is certain resistance from the perpetrator, or a clear and distinct bad will (3), without the need to resort to the judiciary to issue a ruling that compels individuals to do so (4).

The privilege of direct execution is the administration's conduct of the administrative way by issuing administrative decisions and implementing them willingly, and abandoning the judicial way in order to fulfill their rights from individuals.

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The administration, in light of this privilege granted to it, can implement its orders in the face of individuals by force if they refuse to implement them voluntarily without the need to resort to the judiciary, which leads to the enforcement of its rights directly. Those who want to discuss them must resort to the judiciary, while individuals are required, within the scope of private law, to obtain a judgment from the judiciary that serves as an executive authority to enforce their rights, whereas, implementation in civil transactions is not completed without consent or judgment(5).

This privilege guarantees the administration the speedy implementation of its decisions, and this privilege has allocated it without individuals to enable it to perform its mission and to ensure the proper functioning of public facilities. The state and the individual are not equal as long as they act on the basis of sovereignty, authority and privileges (6); That is, it is considered one of the dangerous mechanisms owned by the administration, which affects the rights and freedoms of individuals. Because it authorizes the administration to suspend essential provisions of the law, so in the event that the administration does not resort in advance to the judiciary, individuals are deprived of a great guarantee guaranteed to them by all constitutions, which leads to the violation of individuals' social order(7).

Advantages of the privileged direct execution of management (8)

1- It is assumed in every administrative decision that it was issued based on a valid reason, and whoever claims the opposite must prove that the administrative decision is supposed to be correct until proven otherwise. An important result follows from this, which is that once the administrative decision is issued, it is enforceable and enforceable even if it is incorrect. And whoever wants to dispute it must file a grievance or appeal it through legal procedures.

-Since the administrative decision is issued by the administration with its binding authority according to laws and regulations, and its issuance and implementation do not depend on the consent of individuals, the administration is constantly being defended.

-3The principle is that the decision is implemented voluntarily by individuals, but the administration has the right to resort to direct implementation, or execution through the judiciary, or to use compulsory force to implement the decision.

The problem of the privilege of direct execution does not arise except in the case of decisions that address individuals, asking them to commit to action or to abstain from work, and they have not voluntarily complied (9); This is because the administration bases its use of the right to direct implementation of its

decisions on the presumption of validity that is supposed to be present in those decisions, according to which the integrity, correctness, and conformity of the administrative decision to the law is assumed, and then

It is immediately implementable, and whoever claims the opposite of the presumption of validity must prove that the decision is outside the framework of legality (10).

This privilege cannot be taken for granted, as it does not allow the administration to infringe on the rights of individuals that are protected by the law, nor does it allow it to acquire rights from individuals by its own will, in violation of the rule of law. Because the administration is a public authority subject to the law, and if the decision it issues violates the law, the individual who has the interest may challenge it before the judiciary and demand the restitution of the rights that the administration has seized without right (11).

Based on the foregoing, the direct execution privilege decided for the administration does not entitle it to it, but rather places it in a better position vis-à-vis individuals. The individual cannot obtain his rights before others except after filing a lawsuit before the judiciary and deciding on it by a court ruling that he will implement after that. As for the administration, it has the right to obtain its rights from individuals without the need to resort to the judiciary. Individuals may bring the matter to court if they see that the administration has violated a right assigned to them. This is because the administration in its disputes with individuals is in most cases in the center of the defendant, and the individuals bear the burden of filing cases against the administration to claim their rights.

The nature of the direct execution franchise

In the face of this privilege granted to the administration, several theories have arisen about the nature and extent of the privilege of direct execution. And whether it is a general concession for the administration or it is an exceptional way and in certain cases, taking into account the nature of the administration's work and its needs in exceptional circumstances, and despite these conflicting opinions, other opinions emerged that try to reconcile them with the following demands.

Hard-line theory

Its content is that the administration has a general advantage in direct implementation, and that it can take its right on its own without an intermediary. That is, it has the authority to direct implementation, and it can also implement its decisions on its own without the need to resort to the judiciary to obtain an executable judgment even if that implementation relates to others and affects their rights, and this theory has resulted in the following results:

A- Individuals are obligated to obey that execution.

B - Judicial oversight does not stop this implementation except in exceptional cases.

C- The administration is obligated to exercise this privilege, as it is not free to resort to normal execution as it sees fit, but rather it must use the direct implementation method unless it is expressly prohibited.

D- The results of this execution lead to the administration being always in the position of the defendant.

The summary of all this is that the principle is the management's exercise of the privilege of direct implementation, and there are those who see otherwise. Where direct implementation is defined as: "The right of the administration to implement its decisions and orders on individuals by compulsory force without permission from the judiciary." (12) The exception is its resort to normal methods of implementation like other persons of private law. However, critics of this theory believe that it has deviated from the concept of freedom Individuals and their defense, and took the side of the authority of the administration, and tried to support and support it by deciding this privilege despite its seriousness, based on the idea of the authority that the administration enjoys as part of the executive authority. Administrative is restricted in conducting its activities with an objective restriction, which is public utilities (13).

Legal theory

It is the theory adopted by the French jurist (La Friere) who did not acknowledge that direct execution is a privilege for the administration that does not have the right to conduct work or grant itself a privilege that has not been decided by the legislator and defined his opinion that: "The task of the legislator is to prevent abuse and the disadvantages that may result from the use of legal licenses; The legislator indicates the cases in which abuse or disadvantages reach the level of crime or disturbance, and specifies for the administrative or judicial authorities the means by which they can prevent disturbance or punish the crime. And if the means approved by the legislator is not able to fully perform its duty, which will result in the occurrence of An imbalance in the system and the necessity for its stability due to the legal situation, this does not allow the public authorities to grant themselves a privilege and create for themselves rights that were denied by the legislator" (14).

The administration does not act except for the implementation of the laws and within their scope, and the administrative authority cannot violate the limits of the law by imposing it on anything other than the meaning for which it was set or deciding a penalty that was not stipulated by the legislator, and that any order must be issued in accordance with the law, and every act that deviates the administration from the law does not It is nothing but control and tyranny. This opinion is considered a defense of the freedoms of individuals against the administration, and a denial of it to enjoy any power, and it is decided that the power is in the hands of the

legislator and he is the owner of the right to exercise it, and it tends to make this right to management in an exceptional way, with explicit provisions that the administration cannot break with(15).

The objection to this opinion is that it included the status of implementation of laws and regulations and did not include how the administration obtains its rights through direct implementation (16).

Several opinions differed between the two theories. In the opinion (Shabir Ostland), direct implementation is an act contrary to general principles of law, and poses real risks to individuals. Therefore, he only sees it as an exceptional way for the administration, and it must not use it except in the case of necessity and the present danger to maintain security and public order(17).

While Valine believes that the administration has the right to enjoy the privilege of direct execution as a general principle; This is in order to be able to perform its urgent functions related to protecting the security and safety of the state and the preservation of its entity. He believes that it has the right to use this privilege also when implementing laws and regulations when they are devoid of criminal sanction, or in the event of necessity that calls for speedy implementation to avoid dangers and damages threatening public security (18).

Combinational theory

It is based on the middle position between the two previous opinions according to which direct implementation is not an absolute right, but exceptions are made to it and the administration may waive it(19).

In Egypt and Jordan, contemporary administrative jurisprudence (20) generally tends to support the second opinion, as direct implementation is an exceptional method that the administration may not resort to except in specific exceptional cases, and that the general principle is the need to follow the judicial path and obtain an enforceable judgment to resolve the dispute between the administration And individuals.

Direct execution is therefore possible, but it is not permissible to use it unless the obedience of the taxpayers can be obtained by another means, so it has a clear precautionary nature, so the privilege of direct execution is not, except in very exceptional cases, and within a scope clearly defined by the judiciary. This is because using it in an arbitrary manner leads to a conviction by the judiciary (21).

We truly believe that this theory is the closest to logic and reason, so that freeing the hand of the administration in order to implement its decisions in the way it deems appropriate, without any regard for the rights and freedoms of individuals, is considered a privilege over a privilege, since the administration is always stronger even under normal circumstances without exceptional.

Controls of applying the privilege of direct execution

Due to the seriousness of this method - and because it is considered an exceptional means - it is compliant with certain cases, and the administration is committed to applying it with specific conditions and controls in order to give legitimacy to direct implementation, and the cases that the administrative judiciary has committed to, which is the absence of punitive sanctions, and the existence of an explicit legislative text that allows the administration to use direct implementation And the state of necessity, we explain it through the following demands, which are (22):

It is the case in which there is no legal way or criminal sanction that can be followed to punish the person concerned and compel him to implement the decision imposed on him (23).

This is what the French judiciary settled on, where it ruled: "When it is impossible to take any legal measure to resort to criminal courts or to take an administrative sanction, the administration may resort to direct implementation "(24).

So resorting to the judge is the normal way of implementation in order to impose a punitive penalty in the case of failure to implement the administrative decision, but if there is no such penalty in the case of housing confiscation, the administration has to resort to direct execution(25).

The punitive penalty aims to deter the wrongful behavior of individuals, and this penalty may be criminal or administrative, and the penalty is a judicial decision, while the administrative penalty is a single administrative decision issued by an administrative authority and represents a threat to public freedoms, as the administration enjoys exceptional authority regarding administrative sanctions and is considered an adversary and judgment At the same time (26).

However, there are several guarantees governing the exceptional authority of the administration, represented in the necessity of a legal text permitting the system of administrative sanctions, in implementation of Article 34 of the Constitution, given that the legislator is the guarantor of public freedoms, and the administrative penalty must also be consistent with Article 8 of the Declaration of Human Rights (27).

Based on the foregoing, it can be said that the judiciary in France allows the administration to resort to direct implementation in this case in pursuance of the rule of law, not to achieve private purposes, and this requires that individuals have gone out of the rule of laws and regulations and those legislation did not include a penalty for violating them. The administration does not resort to direct implementation unless it has no other means to rely upon to implement the administrative decision, even if there is no legislative text that allows it to do so considering that this is what is required by the necessity of respecting the laws and administrative decisions that put it into practice(28).

Existence of an explicit provision that allows management to use direct implementation

To activate direct implementation, there must be a legislative text that allows the administration to direct implementation, and if there is no such text that gives legitimacy for the administration to implement direct implementation, it does not have the right to do it, and examples of it in France are:

Law of July 3, 1877, Article 21, which is now 15-2221.L of the Defense Law, and the French Constitutional Council resorted to the rule in its ruling issued in 1993 (29), and the Court of Dispute followed the guidance of the Constitutional Council, applying the aforementioned rule in its ruling issued in 1994(30).

Examples of it in Egypt are:

A- Law No. 141 of 1944 which gives the administration the power to directly implement the detention of mentally ill patients and return them to the hospital if they escape from it.

B- Law 111 of 1951 and its amendments, which give the administration the right to deduct a quarter of the salary in specific cases exclusively.

C- Law 308 of 1955 which gives the administration the right to take administrative seizure measures in the event that the state's dues are not fulfilled.

D- Law 371 of 1956 which gives the administration the right to close public shops in the cases specified by law.

In Jordan, the legislator created the privilege of direct implementation in some laws with explicit texts that give the administration the implementation of its decisions through it, including:

-The Emiri Funds Collection Law No. 6 of 1952 and its amendments: Article (6 / c) stipulates the following: "The taxpayers whose names are published in the Official Gazette, and who fail to pay the required sums after the lapse of (60) days from the date of publication, their money may be seized. Legally, by a decision of the administrative ruler, to collect the princely funds, and to be sold if payment has not been made, or the necessary settlement takes place within the period specified by the administrative governor if it is from the transferred funds, but if it is from the immovable property, it is sold after the lapse of one year from the date of confiscation.

-2Public Security Law No. (38) Of 1965: Article (9) thereof specifies cases of resorting to the use of physical force for public security personnel. The use of force to the extent necessary to perform their duties provided that its use is the only means for that. The use of weapons is restricted in the circumstances and for the following reasons..... :

-3Administrative Formations Law No. 47 of 2000: Article (23) stipulates that: "The governor may take the necessary measures to provide food supplies, prevent their storage in order to monopolize them, and raise their prices".

Temporary Public Health Law No. 54 of 2002 and its amendments: Article (61 / b) stipulates that: "The minister may decide to close the place where the violation occurred, close water sources and networks, and seize the mechanisms and machines that cause damage that he deems appropriate, until the violation is removed." (31).

Case of necessity

With the certainty that the existence of the legal text provides legitimacy in the event of resorting to direct implementation, but that the text remains man-made and on paper, and until this is done, it remains until we are in front of the fait accompli. It is the state of necessity to activate it in a way that removes risks and achieves benefits.

This is because laws came to regulate the behavior of individuals within society in normal circumstances, and in these familiar circumstances they are obligated to implement legislation, and if the state of necessity arises, it is permissible for the administration to break the laws to confront the state of necessity, with the aim of protecting the state and its citizens. This does not result in harm to individuals, because breaking laws in such circumstances is decided only in their interest, and examples of the state of necessity include the state of war, the spread of epidemics and diseases, or the presence of disturbances within the state (32), and this is what the French Council of State confirmed by saying: "Administrative bodies, in exceptional circumstances, may take measures that exceed the limits of their normal jurisdiction with the aim of meeting the needs of the moment very quickly ".(33).

This was explained by the government commissioner (Romieu), saying: "The essence of the role played by the administration is to act promptly, to use public power without delay and without measures. And that is when the direct public interest requires it. When a house burns down, one will not ask the judge for permission to send firefighters to it (34).

The Egyptian judiciary also made clear through this during the ruling of the Supreme Administrative Court by saying: "However, the imperative of a state of necessity that finds itself facing imminent danger requires that it intervene immediately to maintain security, tranquility and public health, so that if you wait until the court's ruling is issued, grave dangers will result. Hence, the administrative judiciary in Egypt established that the state of necessity does not exist unless there are four pillars:

First: There is a sudden serious threat to order and security.

Second: That it be the work of necessity issued by the administration, and it is the only means of preventing the risk.

Third: That the work is absolutely necessary, not exceeding the necessity.

Fourth: That this work be carried out by the employee in charge of his job.

-These pillars go back to two well-known foundations that necessities permit prohibitions, and necessity is valued by its extent“ (35).

The Supreme Court of Justice judiciary previously defined the conditions of the state of necessity by saying: “We find that the following are required to invoke the provisions of necessity:

-1The existence of a grave danger threatening public order.

-2That this risk cannot be paid by the usual legal means.

-3That he be the pioneer of the administration in its intervention to achieve the public interest alone.

-4The interest of individuals should not be sacrificed for the sake of the public interest except to the extent that necessity dictates. That is, the administration does not abuse its procedures (36).

Based on the foregoing, the increase in the authority of the administration vis-à-vis individuals, and its lack of compliance to a large extent with the principle of legality, is not taken at all, but rather is determined by what was stated in the provisions of the judiciary and administrative law That is, exit, as some see it, is a partial departure from the principle of legality. Because this principle remains in place and applied, but in a way that differs from the forms in which it is applied during normal times, because the idea of legitimacy in the state is permanent and permanent. However, the controls for this idea taken in case of necessity and exceptional circumstances differ from what is followed regarding it under normal circumstances to be elastic broad in scope in the first case, and narrow and rigid in the second case(37).

And since the direct implementation is an exceptional way, and the status of a privilege for the administration, it has the right to withdraw from it and leave it, and to return to the normal way. That is, the judicial road (38). This is what the Egyptian judiciary emphasized by saying: “Direct execution is not the rule in the management’s treatment of individuals. Rather, the principle is that the administration - like that of individuals - resort to the judiciary to fulfill its rights, Public interest”(39).

The privilege of direct execution - if its conditions are fulfilled through the existence of the legal text that permits recourse to it and the availability of the case of necessity - places the administration in a higher position and stronger than the position of individuals. Because she is able to forcibly trace her rights from individuals without her commitment to file lawsuits against them, and for that, they have the right to resort to the judiciary to discuss them. And that is through the supporting claim with the necessary arguments and documents, at a time when the administration is already provided with evidence in a better and easier position than the individual in the administrative case, as he stands in the position of the weak; Because it originally bears the burden of proof and is usually heavy(40).

Results:

1-The direct execution privilege is one of the privileges granted to the administration through which it is entitled to claim its rights from individuals without the need for the judiciary to intervene, in order to quickly implement administrative decisions, in order to ensure the smooth functioning of public facilities and to achieve the public interest.

2-The direct execution privilege gives the administration the right to suspend substantial legal texts. However, this does not give it a right, but rather provides it with a better position over individuals.

3-The theories address the privilege of direct implementation, although it is based on the administration’s right to do so, but it must take into account the public rights and freedoms of individuals.

4-The controls for applying the privilege of direct execution are different among the legal systems, so we find that in France there are three cases, which are the absence of punitive sanctions, the presence of an explicit legislative text, and the case of necessity, but in both Egypt and Jordan the matter is based on the existence of an explicit legislative text Provides for this and only case of necessity.

5-The administration, while it has the privilege of direct implementation, and work to implement it, has the right at the same time to withdraw from it and leave it and to go the normal way through the judiciary.

Recommendations:

1-The direct execution privilege should not be taken by the administration for its launch under the pretext of speedy enforcement of its decisions and the proper functioning of public facilities, but rather it must be applied in the narrowest limits.

2-In the case of resorting to the privilege of direct execution, it must take into account the public rights and freedoms of individuals, and not be a sword hanging over them, otherwise this is considered a privilege over the privileges that they always enjoy.

3-So that we do not get to the administration resorting to the privilege of direct execution and its reversal, it must be careful from the beginning in order to resort to the judicial way to obtain its rights from individuals.

4- Following the approach taken by the French legislator when he added a third condition to control the application of the privilege of direct execution, in order to search for punitive penalties before initiating direct implementation through the legal text that permits this and the availability of the state of necessity, in order to take into account the rights and public freedoms of individuals.

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